

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Cathepsin B (UniProt ID: P07858) for use in western blot

Donovan Worrall¹, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Riham Ayoubi¹, Edward A. Fon¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

Cathepsin B is a lysosomal cysteine involved in protein degradation and contributes to processes such as antigen processing, apoptosis, and tissue remodeling. Here we have characterized thirteen Cathepsin B commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: P07858, *CTSB*, Cathepsin B, APP secretase, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

In humans, the cysteine cathepsin family consists of 11 members: CTSB, CTSC, CTSF, CTSH, CTSK, CTSL, CTSL2, CTSO, CTSS, CTSW, and CTSZ (1). Most cysteine cathepsins function as endopeptidases, breaking peptide bonds within their protein substrates. Cathepsin B, encoded by the *CTSB* gene, exhibits both aminopeptidase and carboxypeptidase activities. Mutations in the *CTSB* gene have been associated with cancer and neurodegenerative diseases (1, 2). Cathepsin B regulates autophagy (3, 4) and is involved in tumorigenesis (5-7) and immune responses (8-11).

Cathepsin B is initially synthesized as a prepropeptide, which is cleaved into a 46 kDa pro-Cathepsin B. The pro-Cathepsin B is then further cleaved in the late endosome into a 33 kDa single-chain mature form. In the lysosome, the single-chain mature form is processed into a 24–27 kDa double heavy chain form and a 5 kDa light chain (12).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (13-15). Here we evaluated the performance of thirteen commercial antibodies for Cathepsin B for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Cathepsin B properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (16).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (17).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (18, 19). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (13). The HAP1 expresses the Cathepsin B transcript at 6.0, which is above the average range of cancer cells analyzed. A *CTSB* KO HAP1 cells were obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1).

To screen the antibodies by western blot, WT and *CTSB* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all thirteen Cathepsin B antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

In conclusion, we have screened thirteen Cathepsin B commercial antibodies by western blot by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (13). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Cathepsin B were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Cathepsin B in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

The underlying data for this study linked below can be found on Zenodo, an open-access repository for which YCharOS has its own collection of antibody characterization reports.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Cathepsin B antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Cathepsin B only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Cathepsin B experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (16). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (16). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (20, 21).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520. Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A15999. Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-goat secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21432.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *CTSB* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) Or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

References

1. Olson OC, Joyce JA. Cysteine cathepsin proteases: regulators of cancer progression and therapeutic response. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2015;15(12):712-29.
2. Ketterer S, Gomez-Auli A, Hillebrand LE, Petrera A, Ketscher A, Reinheckel T. Inherited diseases caused by mutations in cathepsin protease genes. *FEBS J*. 2017;284(10):1437-54.
3. Iwama H, Mehanna S, Imasaka M, Hashidume S, Nishiura H, Yamamura KI, et al. Cathepsin B and D deficiency in the mouse pancreas induces impaired autophagy and chronic pancreatitis. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11(1):6596.
4. Man SM, Kanneganti TD. Regulation of lysosomal dynamics and autophagy by CTSB/cathepsin B. *Autophagy*. 2016;12(12):2504-5.
5. Bian B, Mongrain S, Cagnol S, Langlois MJ, Boulanger J, Bernatchez G, et al. Cathepsin B promotes colorectal tumorigenesis, cell invasion, and metastasis. *Mol Carcinog*. 2016;55(5):671-87.
6. Vasiljeva O, Papazoglou A, Kruger A, Brodoefel H, Korovin M, Deussing J, et al. Tumor cell-derived and macrophage-derived cathepsin B promotes progression and lung metastasis of mammary cancer. *Cancer Res*. 2006;66(10):5242-50.
7. Ruan J, Zheng H, Rong X, Rong X, Zhang J, Fang W, et al. Over-expression of cathepsin B in hepatocellular carcinomas predicts poor prognosis of HCC patients. *Mol Cancer*. 2016;15:17.
8. Ma KM, Chen X, Liu WH, Chen SH, Yang CL, Yang J. CTSB is a negative prognostic biomarker and therapeutic target associated with immune cells infiltration and immunosuppression in gliomas. *Sci Rep-Uk*. 2022;12(1).
9. Wang HF, Yang Q, Liu XC, Xu ZL, Shao ML, Li DX, et al. Structure-based discovery of dual pathway inhibitors for SARS-CoV-2 entry. *Nat Commun*. 2023;14(1).
10. Gonzalez-Leal IJ, Röger B, Schwarz A, Schirmeister T, Reinheckel T, Lutz MB, et al. Cathepsin B in Antigen-Presenting Cells Controls Mediators of the Th1 Immune Response during Infection. *Plos Neglect Trop D*. 2014;8(9).
11. Michallet MC, Saltel F, Preville X, Flacher M, Revillard JP, Genestier L. Cathepsin-B-dependent apoptosis triggered by antithymocyte globulins: a novel mechanism of T-cell depletion. *Blood*. 2003;102(10):3719-26.
12. Gaire BP, Subedi L, Teramoto H, Hu B. The Role of Cathepsin B in Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury After Stroke. In: Pluta R, editor. *Cerebral Ischemia*. Brisbane (AU)2021.
13. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife*. 2023;12.
14. Carter AJ, Kraemer O, Zwick M, Mueller-Fahrnow A, Arrowsmith CH, Edwards AM. Target 2035: probing the human proteome. *Drug Discov Today*. 2019;24(11):2111-5.
15. Licciardello MP, Workman P. The era of high-quality chemical probes. *RSC Medicinal Chemistry*. 2022;13(12):1446-59.
16. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Bolivar SG, Alende C, Moleon VR, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization (Version 1). *Protocol Exchange*. 2024.
17. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made *F1000Research* 2023. 2023;12:1344.
18. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolahdouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife*. 2019;8.
19. Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Schlaifer I, Ayoubi R, Edwards AM, Durcan TM, et al. Identification of highly specific antibodies for Serine/threonine-protein kinase TBK1 for use in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. *F1000Res*. 2022;11:977.
20. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2023;51(D1):D358-D67.
21. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech*. 2018;29(2):25-38.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC006132c001	CVCL_SK16	HAP1	<i>CTSB</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Cathepsin B antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab125067**	1007912-1	AB_10972167	recombinant mono	EPR4323	rabbit	0.28	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab214428**	GR3444644-6	AB_2848144	recombinant mono	EPR21033	rabbit	0.49	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab270998**	GR3402831-2	n/a	recombinant mono	EPR24353-25	rabbit	0.46	Wb
Abcam	ab58802*	GR3447082-7	AB_940824	monoclonal	CA10	mouse	0.10	Wb
ABCD Antibodies	ABCD_AI867**	10/27/2023	AB_3076342	recombinant mono	2A2	rabbit	0.001	other
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF953	FWN0222031	AB_355738	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb, IP, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP1-19797	A4	AB_1641648	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	31718**	1	AB_2687580	recombinant mono	D1C7Y	rabbit	0.05	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX134724	43537	AB_2887332	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.62	Wb
Proteintech	12216-1-AP	00108078	AB_2086929	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.60	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32651**	YE3913382A	AB_2809928	recombinant mono	JA11-02	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35194**	YE3913563	AB_2849098	recombinant mono	ARC0395	rabbit	0.80	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-42576*	YE3913385B	AB_2911717	monoclonal	J11-A11	mouse	2.00	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, n/a=not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (13)

Figure 1: Cathepsin B antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Cathepsin B antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Cathepsin B antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab125067** at 1/1000, ab214428** at 1/100, ab270998** at 1/100, ab58802* at 1/200, ABCD_AI867** at 1/5, AF953 at 1/1000, NBP1-19797 at 1/100, 31718** at 1/300, GTX134724 at 1/100, 12216-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-32651** at 1/100, MA5-35194** at 1/100, MA5-42576* at 1/5000. Predicted band size: 37.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.